

D6.1 – Website and communication material

WP6 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Replication strategies

Document Detail

Due date	v1: 31/08/2024; v2: 28/02/2025
Actual delivery date	v1: 30/08/2024; v2: 28/02/2025
Lead Contractor	Environment Park S.P.A.
Version	2.0
Prepared by	Ilaria Schiavi
Input from	Environment Park SpA
Reviewed by	Snam, Resolvent, Fondazione Politecnico di Milano

Co-funded by
the European Union

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of ENVIPARK and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

Table of Content

Executive Summary	2
1 Introduction	3
2 H ₂ SHIFT visual identity	3
3 Templates for presentations and deliverables	4
4 Social media accounts and channels	4
5 Official presentation of the project	5
6 Project Brochure and roll up	5
7 H ₂ SHIFT project website	9
8 Next steps	15
9 Annex I: Brand book	16
10 Annex II: Official project presentation (version August 2024)	26
12 Annex III: Official project presentation (version January 2025)	46

Executive Summary

This document outlines the work undertaken in the preparation and evolution of H₂SHIFT communication material, including the project website.

The communication material prepared of the project included (in bracket the month of delivery and details of further updates):

- The visual identity of the project (M6);
- Templates for presentations and deliverables (M6);
- Headers for the LinkedIn project page and the YouTube channel; headers and avatar for the X project account (M6);
- A PowerPoint presentation of the project (first version: M6; further version M11);
- The project brochure and roll up (M8);
- The website (launched in M6 and updated in the following months).

The visual identity of the project defines the style of the main communication elements to be used to identify uniquely the project: font, colour palette, logo. All other communication materials are based on these elements.

At M6, templates for presentations and deliverables, visual elements for the project social media accounts, a first version of a project presentation and the project website have been prepared. The first version of the project brochure and roll up were prepared for M8 and will be updated throughout the project with the rest of the communication material.

The project website was launched at the end of August 2024. The project website structure and content were curated by Environment Park, with support of service providers for the web publication. The overall style is in line with the visual identity of the project. Published texts were agreed upon, provided and/or reviewed by the Project Coordinator and the project partners.

The website is destined to the general public and has the main objective of communicating aims, inform on facilities and participants and timeline of project H₂SHIFT. Specific sections dedicated to each test line have been published with initial information. A section with the project news has also been opened. Further sections will be activated in the next months to make publications available, including public deliverables, articles and open access papers, generated by H₂SHIFT. The website will also be the main source of information for the Open Calls planned in the second part of project.

The social media accounts were activated in September 2024 and have been used to both inform about the project and to support the activities of the projects requiring wide dissemination.

Further versions of this document will provide updates about the communication material produced in the period. More specifically, while version 1 covered the period up to M6, version 2 (this version) covers up to M12. They will also record the evolution of the website, which will be regularly updated to include, for instance: project publications and news, development of the test lines, results of the showcases, opening of the project calls and further results.

1 Introduction

The H₂SHIFT project aims to establish the first innovation and excellence hub for innovative hydrogen production technologies open to startups and SMEs from Europe and globally. Communication material is to be prepared and made available to support awareness raising and dissemination of the project aims and of the technical activities to be undertaken to achieve this objective. This supports the strategy for dissemination and communication, as explained in deliverable D6.2.

The communication material includes (in bracket the month of delivery and details of further updates):

- The visual identity of the project (M6);
- Templates for presentations and deliverables (M6);
- Headers for the LinkedIn project page and the YouTube channel; headers and avatar for the X project account (M6);
- The brochure and roll up (M8);
- An official PowerPoint presentation of the project (version 1: M6; version 2: M11);
- The website.

2 H₂SHIFT visual identity

The visual identity of the project defines the style of the main communication elements to be used to identify uniquely the project: font, colour palette, logo. All other communication materials are based on these elements.

The colour palette and font were agreed with the Coordinator, while the logo was chosen amongst a few alternatives proposed by ENVI with the support of a graphic designer.

The final logo (and pictogram or simplified version) chosen is illustrated below.

Figure 1 Final logo and pictogram of H₂SHIFT

A Brand book was made available to all partners defining the rules for the use of the font, colour palette, logo and pictogram. The Brand book is attached in Annex 1.

3 Templates for presentations and deliverables

On the basis of the visual identity developed, templates for Deliverables and Power Point presentations were prepared and made available to the Consortium on time for the first deliverables due at M3 of the project. An example of the deliverable template is shown in this document, while the Power Point template is exemplified in the official project presentation attached in Annex II and Annex III.

4 Social media accounts and channels

The headers for the LinkedIn and X accounts and for the YouTube channel are represented below.

Figure 2 H2SHIFT LinkedIn page header

Figure 3 H2SHIFT X profile page header and avatar

Figure 4 Mock-up of H₂SHIFT YouTube channel

The accounts have been activated and populated according to an editorial plan that has covered:

- The presentation of the project objectives;
- An introduction of each partner;
- The description of the test lines;
- Relevant events, including: General Assembly in October, attendance to the Hydrogen Week 2024 and to the HyVolution exhibitions, publicity of the HyVolution dissemination event.

The social media channels were also used to support project activities such as:

- The launch of a survey to assess interests of potential test line users (WP3 activity);
- The launch of the showcase for test line 9 (WP4 activity).

5 Official presentation of the project

The first version of the project presentation, developed for M6, is provided in Annex II. A further refined version was produced in M11 (Annex III) and was used to introduce the project at a workshop held on January the 28th, 2025 during the HyVolution exhibition.

6 Project Brochure and roll up

H₂SHIFT project brochure is an A4 booklet that illustrates the main characteristics of the project in line with the project description. It can be used as a folder to collect specific information sheets on the single test lines, to be produced for providing in depth technical information on the facilities of the OITB. A scaled down representation of the external pages and internal pages of the brochure is provided below.

A project roll up was also developed, and it is illustrated in the next page. That version of the project roll up has been printed and used in the two events attended during the first 12 months of the project, see below.

Figure 7 Project roll-up at the Hydrogen Week 2024, Brussels and at HyVolution 2025, Paris

The poster features a QR code in the top right corner. The main title is "H2shift" in a large, stylized font. Below it, the text reads "SERVICES FOR HYDROGEN INNOVATION FACILITATION AND TESTING". A sub-headline states: "Project H2SHIFT is the first Open Innovation Test Bed for innovative low carbon hydrogen production technologies".

The central part of the poster is a dark blue box with white and light blue text. It says: "THROUGH H2SHIFT SINGLE ENTRY POINT INNOVATIVE STARTUPS AND SMEs CAN ACCESS TO". Below this, it lists "TESTING SERVICES AT SEVEN TECHNOLOGY TEST LINES":

- Advanced Electrolysis (AEMEL / AEMEL)
- Biohydrogen production (BIOGAS / BIOMETHANE / BIOMETHANOL)
- Direct-solar H₂ production (THERMO / PHOTO)
- Offshore H₂ production

Below the test lines, it lists "TECHNOLOGY UPSCALING SERVICES" and "BUSINESS ACCELERATION SERVICES".

The bottom of the dark blue box says "INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS" and "H2SHIFT will experiment the service offer through internal showcases and two waves of calls open to all companies."

At the bottom of the poster, there is a white bar with the website "h2shift.eu" and social media icons for LinkedIn and Twitter. Below this bar is a grid of logos for partners and funders, including Snam, Politecnico Milano, IREC, Viver, Resolvent, H2B, Youwind, and the European Union.

Figure 8 Project roll-up

7 H₂SHIFT project website

H₂SHIFT project website can be found at the link: <https://h2shift.eu/>

The website aims to provide the general public with information about the project (objectives, timeline), a description of the services, including a first overview of the test lines, and a description of the partners involved.

The first release (August 2024) of the website was structured as follows:

- Homepage: links to a description of the project, its main objective, the SEP and the Consortium.
- Project section: with two subsections respectively on: objectives and timeline, and innovation support offer.
- Test lines section: a Europe map showing location of the test lines and boxes dedicated to each test line, linking to one page each where a first overview is provided.
- Consortium section: reporting the list of all partners with link to a page each describing the partner and its role within H₂SHIFT project.
- News and events: a page dedicated to project news and events.

Some corrections were implemented to ensure better description of the activities of the partners and also to insert a facility to collect subscribers to the newsletter/contact requests.

Figure 9 Top half of the homepage of H₂SHIFT project website

Figure 10 Acknowledgement of funding on H₂SHIFT project website, with contact information and link to social media accounts

H₂SHIFT PROJECT

H₂Shift: Services for Hydrogen Innovation Facilitation and Testing

H₂SHIFT project

The project supports the development of hydrogen production technologies alternative to low temperature electrolysis.

Advanced Water Electrolysis

- Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOE)
- Proton Conducting Ceramic Electrolysis (PCCEL)
- Anion Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (AEMEL)

Direct Solar Hydrogen Production

Thermo-chemical water splitting
Photo-electro chemical water splitting

Biohydrogen

Hydrogen from biomass
Hydrogen from biogas
Hydrogen from bioethanol

Offshore

Hydrogen produced in an offshore environment

The development of the target technologies will be implemented through 9 testlines of which 7 technological and 2 supporting upscaling and business development. The testlines are managed by the H₂SHIFT consortium. Access to the testlines will be managed through H₂SHIFT as a single entry point. The project started in March 2024 and will last 48 months. After an initial ramp up period, the testlines will be validated through selected showcases and then through two Open Calls.

Figure 11 Project section page

The key target of H₂SHIFT is to create a platform of technology infrastructure that will represent a solution for companies (startups and SMEs in particular) to carry out tests and advance the upscaling of their technologies, including assessment of circularity by design and of regulatory conformity. The project prioritizes a collaborative approach amongst large industries, SMEs and startups and research OK organisations for launching and accelerating new processes and devices for producing H₂.

5 Objectives

- 01** Increase the speed and scale of the transition to net-zero by developing a hydrogen future-proof growth strategy and kickstarting a large H₂ ecosystem throughout Europe
- 02** Organise a European launchpad leveraging existing knowledge and expertise to co-develop potentially scalable sustainable technology with startups, SMEs, and relevant stakeholders worldwide
- 03** Deliver and validate a fully operational, high-pace, non-equity Open Innovation Test Bed (OITB) at a very fast pace
- 04** Investigate, test, assess, and upscale emerging hydrogen production technologies mentioned in the Agenda Process SRIA
- 05** Craft stories of impact and make sense of the proposed OITB to enable the optimal conditions for hydrogen innovation to emerge and scale-up

Timeline

- 2024 – Launch of SEP**
TEST SERVICES RAMPING UP
While the SEP is established, the test services and testing lines are fully implemented ready for the first validation phase.
- 2025 – Showcasing of testing service**
- 2026/2027 – 1st and 2nd open calls**
- 2028 – End of financed project**

Project progress status

Innovation support offer
Our customers, what is on offer, the support ecosystem, accessibility

H₂Shift project
Services for Hydrogen Innovation Facilitation and Testing

Figure 12 Objectives & Timelines subsection page

Figure 13 Innovation support offer subsection page

Figure 14 Interactive map of test lines in the Test Lines page

TEST LINE #5

Thermochemical water splitting

Politecnico di Torino

Development of materials for supporting direct solar thermolysis and solar thermochemical redox cycles for H₂, CO and O₂ generation from water and CO₂ (chemical looping).

TEST FACILITIES	TEST TYPES	FURTHER SERVICES
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• System for Temperature Programmed Reduction and Oxidation.• Microreactor coupled with online gas analysis.• Solar concentrator for mounting chemical looping reactor.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Characterisation of material's performance in terms of reactivity, structural transformation, also in cycles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Testing of materials in "train reactor" configuration mounted on solar concentrator.

ALL TEST LINES →

Figure 15 Example of a dedicated test line page with an initial description

H₂SHIFT PROJECT

Consortium

H₂SHIFT Consortium is a diversified range of players from academia, industry and business support services, covering the whole value chain of the Open Innovation Testbed.

Figure 16 Snapshot of the Consortium page

8 Next steps

The communication material developed during the first six months of the project will be updated with the development of the project, e.g. adding on to/modifying the relevant pages of the website or the presentation. Similarly, the brochures and roll up will follow the development of the project and be integrated/substituted by updated versions containing significant results achieved to date. For instance, with the validation of the test lines with the showcases, single sheets describing the facilities can be produced.

Further communication material has been created and printed (e.g. roll ups and project brochures) and used to support participation to the first events. Activity on social media will continue, with posts and videos; new pages for the project publications and the Open Calls will be developed. It is expected that the news page of the project will be further populated.

9 Annex I: Brand book

ES
Share

INDEX

- 1 Logo for four-colour printing and Pantone colours logo
- 2 RGB and HEX colours logo
- 3 Grayscale black and white logo
- 4 Monochrom black and white logo
- 5 Negative logo version
- 6 Logo on generic coloured background
- 7 Logo on institutional colour background
- 8 Required minimum distances
- 9 Unsuitable formatting of logo
- 10 Primary font
- 11 System default font

1

Logo for four-colour printing and Pantone colours logo

The four-colour version of the logo is to be used for printed material.

Horizontal

C 99
M 55
Y 17
K 4

PANTONE 7691 C

Pictogram only

C 50
M 0
Y 100
K 0

PANTONE 375 C

2

RGB and HEX colours logo

RGB and HEX versions are to be used in all web and video applications.

Horizontal

R 0
G 98
B 152

#006298

Pictogram only

R 151
G 215
B 0

#97D700

3

Grayscale black and white logo

The use of the logo in grayscale will need to follow the percentages below.

Horizontal

The horizontal logo in grayscale, featuring the text "H2shift" in a bold, sans-serif font. The "H2" is larger and more prominent than the "shift" part.

K 80

Pictogram only

K 40

4

Monochrom black and white logo

Monochrom black and white logo must be used only if it is not possible to print in colour or grayscale.

Horizontal

The horizontal monochrome logo consists of the word "H2shift" in a bold, sans-serif typeface. The "H" is significantly larger than the other letters. A white "2" is positioned between the "H" and the "s", and a white "i" is positioned between the "s" and the "h".

K 100

Pictogram only

5

Negative logo version

Negative logo version must be used only if positive logo versions cannot be used or for black or dark backgrounds.

Horizontal

C	0
M	0
Y	0
K	0

Pictogram only

6

Logo on generic coloured background

Use the coloured logo on pale colour backgrounds. Use the negative version on dark solid colour backgrounds and on photographic backgrounds, as in the examples below.

Pale backgrounds

Dark backgrounds

Photographic backgrounds

Horizontal

Pictogram only

7

Logo on institutional colour background

Use negative version backgrounds on backgrounds in project colours.

Horizontal

C 99
M 55
Y 17
K 4

Pictogram only

C 50
M 0
Y 100
K 0

8

Required minimum distances

A minimum required space around the logo must be ensured. A distance of at least the height of the grey molecule height «x» must be applied as shown below. This is valid for both the full logo and the pictogram only version.

Horizontal

Pictogram only

9

Unsuitable formatting of logo

The logo shall not be broken down, tilted or its proportions changed. Only the colours provided in this guide must be used. On photographic backgrounds, never use colour version but only negative version must be used to ensure visibility.

Primary font

The project font is Ubuntu in its different available intensities.

UBUNTU BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz **1234567890**

UBUNTU MEDIUM

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz **1234567890**

UBUNTU REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

UBUNTU LIGHT

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

11

System default font

Should the primary font not be available, Arial font might be used in its different intensities.

ARIAL BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz **1234567890**

ARIAL MEDIUM

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

ARIAL REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

ARIAL LIGHT

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

10 Annex II: Official project presentation (version August 2024)

SERVICES FOR HYDROGEN INNOVATION FACILITATION AND TESTING

Horizon Europe Project, Grant Agreement number 101137953

Name Surname, Job title, Organisation

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of *(name of the implementing partner)* and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

H₂SHIFT at a glance

- The first **Open Innovation Test Bed for innovative hydrogen production technologies** open to startups and SMEs from Europe and beyond
- A **Single Entry Point** offering unique access to:
 - Hydrogen production testing services including **seven advanced test lines**
 - **Technology upscaling** services
 - **Business support/non-technical** services
- Supporting the **development of new technologies** such as:
 - **High-temperature and AEM electrolysis**
 - **Direct-solar**
 - **Bio-hydrogen** and
 - **Offshore H₂ production**

WHY H₂SHIFT?

Background and rationale

H₂SHIFT enables the further development of technologies alternative to current commercial water electrolysis for the production of low carbon H₂, thus supporting the EU targets.

The target technologies include:

Advanced Water Electrolysis

Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOE)
Proton Conducting Ceramic Electrolysis (PCCEL)
Anion Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (AEMEL)

Direct Solar Hydrogen Production

Thermo-chemical water splitting
Photo-electro chemical water splitting

Biohydrogen

Hydrogen from biomass
Hydrogen from biogas
Hydrogen from bioethanol

Offshore

Hydrogen produced in an offshore environment

H₂SHIFT OBJECTIVES

Supporting innovation in the European hydrogen ecosystem

H₂SHIFT aims to create the **first innovation and excellence hub for innovative hydrogen production technologies** open to startups and SMEs from Europe and beyond. The technology infrastructure will represent a solution for companies (startups and SMEs in particular) to **carry out tests and advance the upscaling of their technologies**, including assessment of circularity by design and of regulatory conformity.

The project prioritizes a **collaborative approach** amongst large industry, SMEs and startups and research organisations for launching and accelerating new processes and devices for producing H₂.

OBJECTIVE 1

Increase the speed and scale of the transition to net-zero by developing a hydrogen future-proof growth strategy and kickstarting a large H₂ ecosystem throughout Europe

OBJECTIVE 2

Organise a European launchpad leveraging existing knowledge and expertise to co-develop potentially scalable sustainable technology with startups, SMEs, and relevant stakeholders worldwide

OBJECTIVE 3

Deliver and validate a fully operational, high-pace, non-equity Open Innovation Test Bed (OITB) at a very fast pace

OBJECTIVE 4

Investigate, test, assess, and upscale emerging hydrogen production technologies mentioned in the Agenda Process SRIA

OBJECTIVE 5

Craft stories of impact and make sense of the proposed OITB to enable the optimal conditions for hydrogen innovation to emerge and scale-up

H₂SHIFT STRUCTURE & MAIN OUTPUTS

WP1. PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION (SNAM)

OUTPUT n°1: Project management and coordination.

WP3. TEST-LINE UPGRADE AND LONG-TERM BUSINESS STRATEGY (POLITO)

OUTPUT n°1: Technical and non-technical upgrade of test-lines to accommodate major target users and enhance of H₂SHIFT long-term business strategy.

WP5. OITB OPEN CALLS (FPM)

OUTPUT n°1: Selection and acceleration of Startups/SMEs.
OUTPUT n°2: Implementation and validation of the Acceleration Programme

WP2. SEP CREATION, GOVERNANCE AND ECOSYSTEM (CDI)

OUTPUT n°1: Creation of a novel legal entity to act as SEP for the interaction with diverse stakeholders.

WP4. OITB VALIDATION VIA SHOWCASES (IREC)

OUTPUT n°1: Validation of test-lines via Showcases.

WP6. DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND REPLICATION STRATEGIES (ENVI)

OUTPUT n°1: Communication and dissemination of project results and outputs.
OUTPUT n°2: Tailoring of exploitation strategies.

H₂SHIFT timeline

Launch of SEP
2024

TEST SERVICES RAMPING UP

While the SEP is established, the test services and testing lines are fully implemented ready for the first validation phase

2025

SHOWCASING OF TESTING SERVICES

The selected showcases will support a first phase of validation of the services of the Open Innovation Test Bed. A match showcase- test line has been established within the H₂SHIFT consortium

Open call: 1st wave
2026

OPEN CALLS VALIDATION OF TESTING SERVICES

The OITB will be further enhanced and tailored to the needs of target users, and the response of the market will be tested through two waves of Open Calls. This second phase of validation will support the definition of the final service offer of the H₂SHIFT OITB, thus improving its long-term sustainability and market relevance/attractiveness.

Open call: 2nd wave
2027

End of financed project
2028

COMMERCIAL OPERATION

After the end of the project, the OITB will operate in the market supporting especially start ups and SMEs and exploring further services/test lines to bring on board

H₂SHIFT partners

FOCUS ON THE TEST LINES

Seven laboratory test lines and two business support services distributed throughout Europe accessible through the SEP

1. High-temperature electrolysis → SPAIN @IREC
2. Anion Exchange Membrane electrolysis → UK @University of Wales
3. Biogas testing → ITALY @SNAM
4. Bioethanol reforming → SPAIN @Technicas Reunidas
5. Thermochemical water splitting → ITALY @Politecnico Torino
6. Photo(electro)catalytic H₂ production → ITALY @Politecnico Torino
7. Production of H₂ in offshore environment → ICELAND @YouWind Renewables

TESTLINE #1: High-temperature electrolysis

Shaping Energy for a Sustainable Future

Offering testing services from the cell to the system level providing coherent and comprehensive outputs for low-TRL SOEL and PCCEL technologies.

Test facilities :

W- to MW-range;
500 and 1000°C temperatures with 95% steam flow and H₂ safe gas atmospheres;
PRIMA platform for real power profile from renewable energy production plants

Test types:

Performance (V-I) and galvanostatic long-term experiments;
Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) at cell level: JRC and other protocols applied

Further services:

Postmortem characterization of the cells and stacks;
Roundtrip evaluation

TESTLINE #2: Anion Exchange Membrane (AEM) Electrolysis

University of
South Wales
Prifysgol
De Cymru

AEM electrolysis testing lines and expertise in supporting manufacturers in developing their industrial scale product

Test facilities :

Long-term testing of 100kW AEM electrolyser

Development of smaller scale electrolysers for addressing specific AEM challenges (stability/durability of materials; water management)

Test types:

System performance testing for continuous improvement

Further services:

Development of full safety analysis;
Scaling up and cost reduction analysis

TESTLINE #3: Biogas reforming

Platform delivering biogas/biomethane and CO₂ for the production of bio-H₂ and testing of CCUS technologies

Test facilities :

Biogas input 5-10Nm³/h for short to long duration tests

Test types:

Continuous input with recovery of bio-h₂ in output for energy production

Further services:

Multiple test-benches with adaptable input (e.g. different gases)

TESTLINE #4: Bioethanol reforming

Supporting the development of bio-ethanol/methanol reforming with purification for mobility –grade hydrogen production

Test facilities :

Up to 20Nm³/h of output;
Syngas generation/
upgrading/ purification;
Integration with different
technologies simulating a full
plant

Test types:

System test with different
feedstock/ water-methanol
mixtures

Further services:

Optimisation of integration
reformer/purification unit;
Support to industrialization
of plant component and
integration in industrial
plants

TESTLINE #5: Thermochemical water splitting

Politecnico
di Torino

Development of materials for supporting direct solar thermolysis and solar thermochemical redox cycles for H₂, CO and O₂ generation from water and CO₂ (chemical looping)

Test facilities :

System for Temperature Programmed Reduction and Oxidation;
Microreactor coupled with online gas analysis;
Solar concentrator for mounting chemical looping reactor

Test types:

Characterisation of material's performance in terms of reactivity, structural transformation, also in cycles

Further services:

Testing of materials in "train reactor" configuration mounted on solar concentrator

TESTLINE #6: Photo-electro-chemical water splitting

Politecnico
di Torino

Development and scale up of photo-electrochemical reactors / photo-electrodes and cells

Test facilities :

Photo-electrocatalytic and electrocatalytic test bench with automated and computerized control of flow rates, P (1-30bar), T (20-150°C)

Test types:

Development of materials and characterisation of material's catalytic performance; performance testing with different input gases

Further services:

Test bench for TRL4 validation of cells; cells scaling up to 2500cm²

TESTLINE #7: Offshore Production of H₂

Renewables

Exploring the business case for production of hydrogen in offshore environment

Test facilities :

Offshore wind park evaluation software with added plug-in for hydrogen production business case

Test types:

Advanced costing tools for hydrogen production, storage & transport from windmill parks; pricing scenarios

Further services:

Integration in overall windmill park business case evaluator according to different pricing scenarios for electricity and hydrogen

TESTLINE #8: Technology upscaling

resolvent

Modelling solutions

Multiphysics simulation to support design and scale up of efficient hydrogen production technologies

Test facilities :

Multiphysics computational modelling of design and performance of new concepts and technologies

Test types:

Digital simulation for conceptual modelling; numerical testing of new concepts/designs; sensitivity analysis; system optimization etc.

Further services:

Simulation platform supporting product innovation from concept to market, including performance modelling and cost optimisation

TESTLINE #9: acceleration services

Non-technical services for the management and support of an acceleration programme for companies accessing the OITB

Non-technical facilities :

Leveraging SNAM
HyAccelerator activities and
models

Support:

Techno-economic and life
cycle assessment;
Policy assessment and
regulation compliance;
Business development;
Create new partnership and
access new solutions;
Professional mentorship

Further services:

Simulation platform
supporting product
innovation from concept to
market, including
performance modelling and
cost optimisation

H₂SHIFT impact

What is on offer

globally innovative startups and SMEs benefiting of a bundled support offer **including cutting-edge facilities, services, and unique expertise** to advance their **hydrogen production technologies** beyond the state-of-the-art, from PoC (Proof of Concept, **TRL 3**)/Validation in laboratory (**TRL4**) to prototypes/systems demonstrated in industrial environments (**TRL7/8**).

The support ecosystem

Organized in a cohesive and collaborative ecosystem linking **research, academia, and industry, and final investors**, which successfully coordinates unrivalled resources, infrastructures, and capabilities, as shaped in a combination of technical services, process upscaling and non-technical services.

Boosting the Clean H₂ JU SRIA on the path towards the deployment and upscaling of highly unmatched and competitive innovative hydrogen production technologies by developing and running an **effective and sustainable OITB**.

Accessibility

Based on a **pay-per-use scalable hub** that circumvents expensive costs for startups and SMEs to access leading-edge innovation facilities and services, in addition to **revenues from selling hydrogen** and biogenic carbon dioxide molecules to the market.

H₂shift

Thank you

Name Surname, Organisation,
Contacts

H₂SHIFT is a Horizon Europe Project, Grant Agreement number 101137953

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of *(name of the implementing partner)* and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

12 Annex III: Official project presentation (version January 2025)

SERVICES FOR HYDROGEN INNOVATION FACILITATION AND TESTING

Horizon Europe Project, Grant Agreement number 101137953

Name Surname, Job title, Organisation

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of *(name of the implementing partner)* and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

H₂SHIFT at a glance

- The first **Open Innovation Test Bed** for **innovative hydrogen production technologies** open to startups and SMEs from Europe and beyond
- A **Single Entry Point** offering unique access to:
 - Hydrogen production testing services including **seven advanced test lines**
 - **Technology upscaling** services (e.g. modelling and simulation)
 - **Business support** services
- Supporting the **development of new technologies** such as:
 - **High-temperature and AEM electrolysis**
 - **Direct-solar**
 - **Bio-hydrogen** and
 - **Offshore H₂ production**

H₂SHIFT partners

Politecnico di Torino

POLITECNICO MILANO 1863

Fondazione Politecnico di Milano

Shaping Energy for a Sustainable Future

TECNICAS REUNIDAS

Electrolysis Technologies

Youwind

Renewables

University of South Wales
Prifysgol De Cymru

WHY H₂SHIFT?

Background and rationale

H₂SHIFT enables the further development of technologies alternative to current commercial water electrolysis for the production of low carbon H₂, thus supporting the EU targets.

The target technologies include:

Advanced Water Electrolysis

Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOE)
Proton Conducting Ceramic Electrolysis (PCCEL)
Anion Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (AEMEL)

Direct Solar Hydrogen Production

Thermo-chemical water splitting
Photo-electro chemical water splitting

Biohydrogen

Hydrogen from biomass
Hydrogen from biogas / biomethane
Hydrogen from bioethanol

Offshore

Hydrogen produced in an offshore environment

H₂SHIFT OBJECTIVES

Supporting innovation in the European hydrogen ecosystem

H₂SHIFT is a **hub of technology infrastructures and supporting services** accessible to startups and SMEs so that they **carry out development tests and advance the upscaling of their technologies.**

The project prioritizes a **collaborative approach** amongst large industry, SMEs and startups and research organisations for launching and accelerating new processes and devices for producing H₂.

OBJECTIVE 1

Investigate, test, assess, and upscale emerging hydrogen production technologies

OBJECTIVE 2

Co-develop potentially scalable sustainable technology with startups, SMEs, and relevant stakeholders worldwide, leveraging on existing knowledge and expertise

OBJECTIVE 3

Establish an Open Innovation Test Bed (OITB), fully operational also beyond the end of the project, to service continuous technological development

OBJECTIVE 4

Enable the optimal conditions for hydrogen innovation to emerge and scale-up

OBJECTIVE 5

Support the EU transition to net-zero by contributing to the establishment of large H₂ ecosystem throughout Europe

H₂SHIFT timeline

Launch of SEP
2024

TEST SERVICES RAMPING UP

While the SEP is established, the test services and testing lines are fully implemented ready for the first validation phase

2025

SHOWCASING OF TESTING SERVICES

The selected showcases will support a first phase of validation of the services of the Open Innovation Test Bed. A match showcase- test line has been established within the H₂SHIFT consortium

Open call: 1st wave
2026

OPEN CALLS VALIDATION OF TESTING SERVICES

The OITB will be further enhanced and tailored to the needs of target users, and the response of the market will be tested through two waves of Open Calls. This second phase of validation will support the definition of the final service offer of the H₂SHIFT OITB, thus improving its long-term sustainability and market relevance/attractiveness.

Open call: 2nd wave
2027

End of financed project
2028

COMMERCIAL OPERATION

After the end of the project, the OITB will operate in the market supporting especially start ups and SMEs and exploring further services/test lines to bring on board

FOCUS ON THE TEST LINES

Seven laboratory test lines and two business support services distributed throughout Europe accessible through the SEP

#	Test lines	Leader
TL1	High-temperature electrolysis	IREC Sharing Energy for a Sustainable Future
TL2	Anion Exchange Membrane electrolysis	University of South Wales
TL3	Biogas Reforming	snam
TL4	Bioethanol Reforming	TECNICAS REUNIDAS
TL5	Thermochemical water splitting	Politecnico di Torino
TL6	Photo(electro)catalytic H ₂ production	Politecnico di Torino
TL7	Production of H ₂ in off-shore environment	Youwind Model
TL8	Technology upscaling services	resolvent Modelling Solutions
TL9	Non-technical Services	CNR IREC ENERGIE RINNOVABILI

- Non H₂ production testing services
- Advanced Water Electrolysis
- Bio-Hydrogen
- Direct Solar to H₂
- Offshore

TESTLINE #1: High-temperature electrolysis

Shaping Energy for a Sustainable Future

Offering testing services from the cell to the system level providing coherent and comprehensive outputs for low-TRL SOEL and PCCEL technologies.

Test facilities :

W- to MW-range;
500 and 1000°C temperatures
with 95% steam flow and H₂ safe
gas atmospheres;
PRIMA platform for real power
profile from renewable energy
production plants

Test types:

Performance (V-I) and
galvanostatic long-term
experiments;
Electrochemical Impedance
Spectroscopy (EIS) at cell
level: JRC and other
protocols applied

Further services:

Postmortem
characterization of the cells
and stacks;
Roundtrip evaluation

TESTLINE #2: Anion Exchange Membrane (AEM) Electrolysis

University of
South Wales
Prifysgol
De Cymru

AEM electrolysis testing lines and expertise in supporting manufacturers in developing their industrial scale product

Test facilities :

Long-term testing of 100kW AEM electrolyser

Development of smaller scale electrolysers for addressing specific AEM challenges (stability/durability of materials; water management)

Test types:

System performance testing for continuous improvement

Further services:

Development of full safety analysis;
Scaling up and cost reduction analysis

TESTLINE #3: Biogas reforming & biomethane decomposition

Platform delivering biogas/biomethane and CO₂ for the production of bio-H₂ and testing of CCUS technologies

Test facilities :

Biogas input 5-10Nm³/h for short to long duration tests

Test types:

Continuous input with recovery of bio-h₂ in output for energy production

Further services:

Multiple test-benches with adaptable input (e.g. different gases)

TESTLINE #4: Bioethanol reforming

Supporting the development of bio-ethanol/methanol reforming with purification for mobility –grade hydrogen production

Test facilities :

Up to 20Nm³/h of output;
Syngas generation/
upgrading/ purification;
Integration with different
technologies simulating a full
plant

Test types:

System test with different
feedstock/ water-methanol
mixtures

Further services:

Optimisation of integration
reformer/purification unit;
Support to industrialization
of plant component and
integration in industrial
plants

TESTLINE #5: Thermochemical water splitting

Politecnico
di Torino

Development of materials for supporting direct solar thermolysis and solar thermochemical redox cycles for H₂, CO and O₂ generation from water and CO₂ (chemical looping)

Test facilities :

System for Temperature Programmed Reduction and Oxidation;
Microreactor coupled with online gas analysis;
Solar concentrator for mounting chemical looping reactor

Test types:

Characterisation of material's performance in terms of reactivity, structural transformation, also in cycles

Further services:

Testing of materials in "train reactor" configuration mounted on solar concentrator

TESTLINE #6: Photo-electro-chemical water splitting

Politecnico
di Torino

Development and scale up of photo-electrochemical reactors / photo-electrodes and cells

Test facilities :

Photo-electrocatalytic and electrocatalytic test bench with automated and computerized control of flow rates, P (1-30bar), T (20-150°C)

Test types:

Development of materials and characterisation of material's catalytic performance; performance testing with different input gases

Further services:

Test bench for TRL4 validation of cells; cells scaling up to 2500cm²

TESTLINE #7: Offshore Production of H₂

Renewables

Exploring the business case for production of hydrogen in offshore environment

Test facilities :

Offshore wind park evaluation software with added plug-in for hydrogen production business case

Test types:

Advanced costing tools for hydrogen production, storage & transport from windmill parks; pricing scenarios

Further services:

Integration in overall windmill park business case evaluator according to different pricing scenarios for electricity and hydrogen

TESTLINE #8: Technology upscaling

resolvent

Modelling solutions

Multiphysics simulation to support design and scale up of efficient hydrogen production technologies

Test facilities :

Multiphysics computational modelling of design and performance of new concepts and technologies

Test types:

Digital simulation for conceptual modelling; numerical testing of new concepts/designs; sensitivity analysis; system optimization etc.

Further services:

Simulation platform supporting product innovation from concept to market, including performance modelling and cost optimization

TESTLINE #9: acceleration services

Non-technical services for the management and support of an acceleration programme for companies accessing the OITB

Non-technical facilities :

Leveraging SNAM
HyAccelerator activities and
models

Support:

Techno-economic and life
cycle assessment;
Policy assessment and
regulation compliance;
Business development;
Create new partnership and
access new solutions;
Professional mentorship

Further services:

Simulation platform
supporting product
innovation from concept to
market, including
performance modelling and
cost optimisation

H₂SHIFT impact

What is on offer

Globally innovative startups and SMEs benefiting of a bundled support offer **including cutting-edge facilities, services, and unique expertise** to advance their **hydrogen production technologies** beyond the state-of-the-art, from PoC (Proof of Concept, **TRL 3**)/Validation in laboratory (**TRL4**) to prototypes/systems demonstrated in industrial environments (**TRL7/8**).

The support ecosystem

Organized in a cohesive and collaborative ecosystem linking **research, academia, and industry, and final investors**, which successfully coordinates unrivalled resources, infrastructures, and capabilities, as shaped in a combination of technical services, process upscaling and non-technical services.

Accessibility

Based on a **pay-per-use scalable hub** that circumvents expensive costs for startups and SMEs to access leading-edge innovation facilities and services, in addition to **revenues from selling hydrogen** and biogenic carbon dioxide molecules to the market.

Boosting the Clean H₂ JU SRIA on the path towards the deployment and upscaling of highly unmatched and competitive innovative hydrogen production technologies by developing and running an **effective and sustainable OITB**.

H₂shift

Thank you

Name Surname, Organisation,
Contacts

H₂SHIFT is a Horizon Europe Project, Grant Agreement number 101137953

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of *(name of the implementing partner)* and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.